

THE ROLE OF THE ENGLISH LITERATURE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE WORLD LITERATURE

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Annotation: *This article gives a brief overview of the origins of English literature, its stages of development, changes in it, and its place in world literature.*

Key words: *world literature, masterpieces, reflection of the history, National literature, The periodisation of the English Literature, cave dwellers, a real or imaginary hero, the warriors in Heorot, Grendel, Dragon.*

Introduction. English literature is a component part of the world literature. Its best national traditions have played an important role in enriching and development of the world literature. English literature consists of the poetry, prose, and drama written in the English language by authors in England, Scotland, and Wales. These lands have produced many outstanding writers.

Main part. English literature is a rich literature. It includes masterpieces in many forms, particularly the novel, the short story, epic and lyric poetry, the essay, literary criticism, and drama. English literature is also one of the oldest national literatures in the Western world. The masters of English literature from the 1300s to the present rank among the world's greatest literary figures. Such names as Geoffrey Chaucer, William Shakespeare, Christopher Marlowe, Daniel Defoe, Charles Dickens, Jonathan Swift, George Gordon Byron, Bernard Shaw, John Galsworthy and many others from English literature are famous all over the world. Their way of writing has influenced a great number of writers, poets and playwrights from other countries.[1]

National literature is the reflection of the history and of the national peculiarities of the people. Each national literature has much in common with the world literary process, but at the same time has its own specific, characteristic features too. One of the characteristic features of the English authors is that they have always been deeply interested in the political and social conditions of their times. In their works, they have described, criticized, and commented on the society in which they lived.

The periodisation of the English Literature is the following :

- Old English Literature.
- Middle English Literature.

- The Renaissance.
- English literature in the Seventeenth Century.
- The Eighteenth Century. (The Age of Reason or Enlightenment).
- The Romantic Age.
- The Victorian Age.
- English Literature at the End of the 19th and the beginning of the 20th century.
- English Literature in the Twentieth Century.

Each of these periods is a step in the development of the English literature, and each of these periods gave the world genuine works with their own voice and individuality. [2]

OLD ENGLISH LITERATURE (500-1100)

For the first eleven hundred years of its recorded history, the island of Britain suffered a series of invasions. The southern part of the island, warmed by the waters of the Gulf Stream, was inviting to outsiders with its mild climate and rich soil. Each invasion brought bloodshed and sorrow, but each also brought a new people with a new culture and these different peoples created a nation.

250,000 years ago the island was inhabited by cave dwellers. Invaders from the Iberian peninsula (Modern Spain and Portugal) overcame their culture about 2000 B.C., erecting Stonehenge - the circle of huge upright stones. Then a new group, the Celts, appeared. Migrating from east, the Celtic people spread throughout Europe before reaching the British Isles around 600 B.C. They used bronze and, later, iron tools and grew crops. Separate Celtic tribes, each with its own King, warred with each other, and erected timber and stone fortresses. Their priests - called druids - conducted sacrifices in forest shrines. The people who lived in Britain at that time were called the Britons.

In the 1st century before our era the powerful State of Rome conquered Britain. The Romans were practical men. They were very clever at making hard roads and building bridges and fine tall houses. The Romans taught Britons many things. But at the end of the 4th century they had to leave Britain because they were needed to defend their own country of the barbaric people.

After Romans' leave, Britain was invaded by the Germanic tribes called Angles, Saxons and Jutes. By the time the Angles and Saxons conquered Britain, they already had their own letters called "runes", but they had no written literature yet, and the stories and poems they made up had to be memorized. Songs and tales that people made up when at work or at war, or for amusement (folk-lore) became wide-spread. There were also professional singers called "bards". They composed songs about events they wanted to be remembered. They sang of wonderful battles and of the exploits of brave warriors. These songs were handed down to their children and

grandchildren and finally reached the times when certain people who were called "scribes" wrote them down. (The word "scribe" comes from the Latin "scribere"- "to write"). [3]

The first major work of English literature is the epic poem "Beowulf".

Beowulf

The beautiful Anglo-Saxon poem "Beowulf" may be called the foundation-stone of all British poetry. It tells of times long before the Angles and Saxons came to Britain. There is no mention of England in it. The poem was composed by an unknown author. Many parts were added later. The whole poem was written down in the 10th century by an unknown scribe. The manuscript is in the British Museum, in London. It is impossible for a non-specialist to read it in the original, so it was translated in the 20th century.

The story (Beowulf)

Long, long ago there lived a king of the Danes named Hrothgar. He had won many battles and gained great wealth. He built a large and beautiful palace (Heorot) and he presented costly gifts to his warriors and gave splendid banquets. But the joy of the king didn't last long. In the dark fens near by there lived a fierce sea-monster Grendel. He wanted to destroy the palace Heorot, as he disliked noise. Grendel looked like a man but was much bigger, and his whole body was covered with long hair, so thick and tough that no weapon could harm him.

One night when the warriors in Heorot were asleep, Grendel rushed in, seized thirty men and devoured them. The next night the monster appeared again. The men defended themselves bravely, but their swords could not even hurt the monster. From that time no one dared to come to Heorot. For twelve years the palace stood deserted. The news of the disaster reached Beowulf, nephew of Higelac, king of the Jutes. Beowulf was the strongest and the bravest of all the warriors. He was said to have the strength of thirty men. He decided to help Hrothgar. With fourteen chosen companions he set sail for the country of the Danes.[4]

Hrothgar gladly welcomed Beowulf and gave a banquet in his honour. Late at night, when the feast was over, all went to sleep except Beowulf. As Beowulf knew that no weapon could kill Grendel, he was ready to fight bare-handed.

Suddenly the man-eater broke into the hall. He seized and devoured one of the sleeping warriors, and then approached Beowulf. A desperate hand-to-hand fight began. It was so terrible that the walls of the palace shook. Beowulf managed to tear off Grendel's arm, and the monster retreated to his den howling and roaring with pain and fury. He was fatally wounded and soon died.

The next night Grendel's mother, a water-witch, came to Heorot to avenge her son's death. While Beowulf was asleep she snatched away one of Hrothgar's

favourite warriors. Beowulf decided to fight the water-witch. He plunged into the water and found the water-witch in her den beside the dead body of her son Grendel. A desperate fight began. At first Beowulf was nearly overcome, as his sword had no power against the monster. But fortunately his glance fell upon a huge magic sword hanging on the wall. Beowulf killed the monster with its help. Then he cut off the heads of Grendel and of the water-witch and carried them to the surface. Heorot was freed forever. Hrothgar poured treasures into Beowulf's hands.

At last the day came for Beowulf to sail home. Everybody regretted his departure. When Beowulf arrived in his own land, he gave all the treasures he had brought to Higelac and the people. Beowulf was admired and honoured by everybody. After the death of Higelac, Beowulf became king of the Jutes.

The merit of the poem lies in the vivid description of the life of that period, in the heroic deeds of Beowulf and in the beauty of the language.[5]

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